

Multi-physics simulation of blowdown phase for an IB LOCA transient

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, the preliminary results of 3D coupling between neutronics, thermal hydraulics, and fuel thermal mechanics are presented. The tool was designed to evaluate physical phenomena impacting neutron kinetics during sudden changes in the thermal hydraulic environment of the PWR core. The focus was put on intermediate break loss of coolant accidents (IB LOCA) since the core blowdown phase is longer compared to large break scenarios, limiting the effectiveness of moderator anti-reactivity feedback. These accidents often feature the appearance of boiling in the moderator fluid and strong heterogeneities both axially and radially in the core. In addition, thermal hydraulic conditions are strongly coupled with fission power distribution, leading to displacement of the hot spot location and thus influencing prediction of maximal peak cladding temperature (PCT), which is one of the key safety criteria for nuclear reactors. The study relies on the CATHARE code for thermal hydraulics and fuel thermal mechanics modeling and the COCAGNE code for neutron kinetics with a 2-energy group diffusion model. The KAIST-1A full-core benchmark specification was used as reactor input. Hereby, the steady-state calculation followed by IB LOCA transient without control rod drop, up to the moment of reflooding of the core is presented.

Keywords: neutronics, thermal hydraulics, LOCA, code coupling, multi-physics simulations

1. INTRODUCTION

For many years now, the loss of coolant accident (LOCA) is studied as one of the worst scenarios for which any pressurized water reactor (PWR) system must be prepared. Thus, safety authorities put paramount importance on design criteria and operation conditions to prevent any severe fuel structure damage leading to radioactive material release or core meltdown. It is done by imposing limits on peak cladding temperature (PCT), which should never be exceeded, and the maximal number of rods, which might fail because of cladding ballooning and rupture during LOCA transient. To ensure a robust design, safety studies are performed with the use of dedicated nuclear engineering codes. Such studies are currently done separately, covering neutronics, thermal hydraulics, and fuel performance domains, while using boundary conditions computed with individual results, based on conservative methods. These are called single-physics methods, while in principle, many physical phenomena are coupled. In fact, because of better computation resources, higher fidelity multi-physics approaches are getting attention for industrial applications. They enable performing best-estimate analysis, quantifying conservatism of previous methods, and improving safety margins. Building a multi-physics method is often done by using the legacy of single-physics methods and a weak coupling approach.

This paper is focused on application of multi-physics coupling between system scale thermal hydraulics and neutronics (TH-N) for IB LOCA simulation. Despite many recent works on TH-N couplings as reviewed by Wang et al. work from 2019 [1], they do not cover LOCA specific issues such as two-phase fluid conditions in PWR core. Exception to this are recent studies using high-fidelity methods done with RELAP5/PARCS by Peakman et al. [2,3]. During LOCA significant axial and radial heterogeneities emerges in the core as an effect of sudden depressurization and loss of coolant from primary circuit.

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The system rapidly reaches saturation pressure causing boiling crisis near the fuel rods, creating void while the nuclear reactions are still taking place. It challenges precise 3D fission redistribution in the core during the transient, that requires more accurate modelling than point kinetics equation (PKE) which is used in system scale thermal hydraulics codes. A recent review on TH and neutronics fuel screening methods made by Gorton et al. from Oak Ridge in 2023 [4] mentioned the limitations of PKE in the system scale code RELAP5 (Reactor Excursion and Leak Analysis Program) and a multi-physics coupling was pointed out as a mean to partially solve its limitations.

2. METHODS

2.1. Computer codes

CATHARE (Code for Analysis of Thermal-Hydraulics during Accident of Reactor and Safety Evaluation) is a system-scale TH code employed by Framatome to predict transient simulations of LOCA [5]. Typically, the prediction of fission power in CATHARE is performed using a 0D neutronic model that solves the PKE. In the presented coupling, the Interface for Code Coupling (ICoCo) was utilized to establish the coupling.

COCAGNE is a deterministic neutron transport code co-developed by EDF (Électricité de France) and Framatome [6]. It offers two distinct solution methods: a simplified spherical harmonics method (SPN) and an exact neutron transport method (SN) for cartesian geometries. COCAGNE facilitates data exchange via a Python interface and is supplied with macroscopic multi-parametric cross sections by the CARABAS assembly lattice code, based on a 281-groups P_{ij} (self-shielding)/MoC(flux) calculation scheme.

COPERNIC is a fuel performance code designed to predict various fuel properties, including porosity, geometrical changes like pellet swelling or enlargement of gas gap, heat conductivity, heat capacity, internal pressure, and high burnup structure, based on the given fuel material composition and the operational history of the reactor [7]. The files generated by COPERNIC are loaded into CATHARE, enabling the modeling of fuel behavior during transients, including cladding strain and rupture models.

2.2. Thermal hydraulic - Neutronic coupling

This study presents a multi-physics coupling framework integrating the CATHARE and COCAGNE codes. The framework is orchestrated by a Python supervisor script, along with input files defining the simulated system, nuclear fuel, and the core configuration. The supervisor script manages the execution of both CATHARE and COCAGNE, facilitating steady-state and transient calculations. Figure 1 illustrates the architecture of the developed coupling and the data exchange processes.

Figure 1. Coupling diagram.

The supervisor manages the temporal coordination of both codes and the exchange of data between them. CATHARE computes the temperature and density fields, while COCAGNE solves the neutron kinetics and provides information about the fission power of the core cells. In this study the homogeneous/assembly model was used, but it is possible to increase fidelity up to the pin-by-pin scale. At each timestep, the two codes exchange these fields and monitor the convergence of their individual solutions before advancing in time. The convergence criterion employed is the relative change in the Euler length of the vector.

2.3. Geometry description and input data

The KAIST-1A core is a numerical benchmark for small PWR core created by N. Z. Cho from Korean Advanced Institute of Science and Technology (KAIST) [8]. It is composed of 52 assemblies, with an imposed initial power of 900 MWth. Five types of assemblies are composing the core:

- UOX-1: uranium oxide assembly enriched at 2.0% ^{235}U .
- UOX-2: uranium oxide assembly enriched at 3.3% ^{235}U .
- UOX-2 (BA-16): uranium oxide assembly enriched at 3.3% ^{235}U and 16 gadolinia pins.
- MOX-1: "tri-zone" (three Pu enrichment zones) mixed oxide assembly with 8.7% enrichment in the central zone, 7.0% in the intermediate zone and 4.3% in the peripheral zone.
- MOX-1 (BA-8): same as MOX-1 assembly with 8 gadolinia pins.

Pins containing burnable poison are enriched in gadolinium isotopes at 9.0% on natural uranium support. The 16 internal assemblies contain B₄C control rods, which were fully withdrawn in the presented study. Figure 2 presents the KAIST core map.

Figure 2. KAIST-1A assembly map - left, core model - middle and system diagram – right.

The cross sections for KAIST were generated across a range of moderator density, moderator temperature, and effective fuel temperature values. For the effective temperature, the Santamarina formula was utilized due to its higher accuracy in cases where the fuel experiences significant temperature variations far from steady-state conditions.

At the thermal hydraulics scale, the core is modeled as a 3D Cartesian space with an 8x8x20 mesh, corresponding to an assembly-by-assembly scale. Each assembly contains 264 fuel rods, represented by a single rod with 20 axial and 23 radial cells. The radial meshing of the fuel rod consists of 19 cells for the pellet, 1 cell for the gas gap, and 3 cells to model the cladding, including the inner and outer oxide layers. The thermal effect of one rod is scaled up by a factor of 264 in the hydraulic mesh corresponding to the given assembly. Figure 2 (middle and right graphics) presents the 3D model of CATHARE and the system diagram, including the upper and lower plenum where boundary conditions are imposed. Inlet flow is assumed to be symmetrical in the current study, but modeling allows imposing different flow patterns as well.

Only the instantaneous fission power evolution was modeled, based on the neutron kinetic solution from COCAGNE. The major fraction of thermal power computed in the cell was assigned to fuel pellet cells and the rest directly to the fluid cell. This approach models the energy originating from neutron scattering and absorption, as well as other nuclear processes occurring in the moderator fluid.

2.4. Simulation of IB LOCA blowdown phase

Initially, the coupled simulation performs a steady-state calculation, where CATHARE solves the thermal-hydraulic fields for the fluid and the thermal-mechanics of the fuel. Concurrently, COCAGNE solves the eigenvalue problem to determine the power distribution. At 68 seconds, the COCAGNE kinetic solver is activated, and at 70 seconds, the IB LOCA transient begins.

The 2-second period at the critical state was simulated using the kinetic solver to ensure the correctness of the steady state. Both codes employed an adaptive timestep, approximately equal to 10 milliseconds.

The transient initiates when a break occurs in one of the primary coolant loops at full core power. This event leads to the depressurization of the primary circuit and the subsequent loss of fluid from the system, a phase known as the blowdown phase. This phase was simulated using boundary conditions based on illustrative studies of IB LOCA. The inlet flow and outlet pressure of the core were imposed to simulate the break. Figure 3 illustrates the imposed boundary conditions.

Figure 3. Boundary conditions used to simulate IB LOCA, outlet pressure – blue, inlet liquid flow – green.

The results presented in the following section were obtained under the assumption of 75% of the KAIST 900 MWth Nominal Power (NP). Operating at 100% NP results in unrealistically high linear power values for some fuel rods, averaging 328 W/cm. From the perspective of realistic thermal-hydraulic conditions for an IB LOCA transient, the KAIST assumptions were not acceptable, as they led to departure from nucleate boiling (DNB) even at steady state. Thus, the internal cells of fuel pellets reached melting temperature. Therefore, simulations at 75% NP were performed to prevent early DNB and uranium oxide melting while maintaining high linear power at the beginning of the transient.

3. RESULTS

To ensure that a steady state was achieved, the relative changes of key parameters for both codes were monitored. For COCAGNE, these parameters included the effective multiplication factor (k_{eff}), thermal neutron flux, and fast neutron flux across the 3D fields. For CATHARE, the six principal parameters of its solver were tracked across the 3D fields. Figure 4 illustrates the convergence of these parameters as a function of the iteration number performed by the coupling.

Figure 4. Relative changes between two consecutive iterations of principal parameters for coupled simulation during steady state, top – COCAGNE, bottom – CATHARE.

Steady state was achieved after 6000 iterations, at which point the relative changes in the main parameters were three orders of magnitude smaller than those observed in the initial iterations. Notably, the relative changes in neutron flux initially increased before decreasing, with fluctuations corresponding to two-phase thermal-hydraulic phenomena (see the correlated changes in void fraction in Figure 4). The neutron flux was analyzed by comparing it to the single-physics calculation with COCAGNE at the beginning of the coupling. Figure 5 illustrates the differences between the steady-state and initial state at the core midplane.

Figure 5. Comparison between initial neutron flux and after obtaining a steady state. Presented for core midplane at 65 s for 75% NP.

It is important to note that a portion of the neutron flux is redirected to the outer assemblies due to changes in the thermal-hydraulic environment. The temperature field of the fuel rods and the density field for the midplane and axial cut of the KAIST core at steady state are shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Temperature field and moderator density for core midplane and axial view at steady state. Presented for core midplane at 65 s for 75% NP.

As the transient begins, the liquid mass decreases rapidly due to the break opening. This triggers a boiling crisis caused by rapid depressurization. Void formation occurs near the hot fuel rods, leading to the emergence of a two-phase flow. The onset of film boiling further deteriorates heat transfer from the fuel rods, resulting in an increase in cladding temperature. Figure 7 illustrates the total liquid mass in the core and the peak cladding temperature during the IB LOCA simulation. The IB LOCA transient initiates at 70 seconds, marked by rapid changes in boundary conditions.

Figure 7. Liquid mass in the core (left) and peak cladding temperature for each assembly (right). The colors correspond to the assembly map, and the purple dotted line indicates the end of the steady state.

Bear in mind, it is important to note that the presented coupling does not include the models for residual power, decay heat and control rod drop, which significantly affects the second peak cladding temperature (PCT), located between core dry-out (around 110 seconds) and reflooding (at 145 seconds). Therefore, the results in this regard are not realistic. However, the influence of stored energy in the fuel due to the instantaneous fission power evolution can be observed. This underscores the importance of the beginning of the transient modeling, as it has a later impact on cladding heating and its peak temperature. Void formation creates an anti-reactivity feedback, decreasing the overall fission power of the core while also altering the local power distribution. Since the fluid conditions at the core inlet remain similar to the initial state while the upper part of the core is partially voided, the power distribution shifts to the lower part of the core. Figure 8 illustrates the density and power distribution in the core at 80 seconds of the simulation, which is 10 seconds after the break opening.

Figure 8. Moderator fluid density and fission power fields at 80 s of simulation during blowdown phase without control rod drop.

4. CONCLUSIONS AND PERSPECTIVES

The presented multi-physics coupling enables the modeling of both neutronics and thermal-hydraulics phenomena with 3D core at the assembly scale during an IB LOCA. This capability facilitates future comparisons with PKE modeling, commonly used in system-scale simulations. Currently, we are developing residual power and decay heat models to more accurately capture the second peak cladding temperature, which is not realistically represented in the current work. Additionally, we plan to perform full system calculations using this coupling, including the modeling of other elements of the primary and secondary circuits, and then compare the results with experimental benchmark data. Furthermore, we are preparing static Monte Carlo neutron transport simulations to further validate the strongly heterogeneous 3D COCAGNE predictions under IB LOCA conditions.

We have encountered challenges in finding high-quality experimental benchmark data for IB LOCA transients that include both neutronics and thermal-hydraulics parameters. This raises a clear need for additional dedicated experiments to validate new multi-physics methods, particularly for LOCA scenarios where experimental data is limited.

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